

Synthesis, Growth and Characterization of Semi Organic Nonlinear Optical Single Crystals of Sodium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate Hippurate

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Abstract

Semi Organic nonlinear optical crystal of Sodium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate Hippurate (SDPH) was synthesized and the crystals were grown by slow evaporation solution growth technique at room temperature using ethanol as solvent. The grown crystals were characterized by Single crystal XRD, Powder XRD, FTIR, UV- VIS - NIR and fluorescence spectral analyses. The crystal structure and lattice parameters were determined by single crystal XRD. The powder X-ray diffraction pattern shows a high degree of crystallinity of the grown crystals. The FTIR spectrum was recorded in the region 1450 - 4000 cm⁻¹ to identify the presence of functional groups. UV - VIS - NIR spectral analysis shows 98% transmission in the entire visible region. Fluorescence spectrum recorded shows a peak at 528 nm. Mechanical properties of the grown crystals were studied using Vicker's micro hardness tester. The SHG efficiency of SDPH was measured by the Kurtz powder technique and the grain size was confirmed by SEM.

Keywords: Organic Compounds, Fluorescence, X – ray diffraction, SHG Efficiency.

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